

Decision aids to support pregnant women’s decision making about peripartum obstetric interventions – a scoping review protocol.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Decision aids (DAs) are tools designed to support patient engagement and enhance communication in healthcare by providing explicit information about care options and helping clarify personal values. During pregnancy, particularly in peripartum care, DAs are increasingly used to assist women in making informed choices about interventions such as labor induction, analgesia, episiotomy, and caesarean section. Despite the known benefits of DAs, including increased knowledge and reduced decision conflict, existing reviews have primarily focused on high-risk populations, leaving a gap in understanding their impact on low-risk pregnancies and the potential to reduce unnecessary obstetric interventions. This scoping review aims to address this gap.

Objectif: The objective of this scoping review is to map all the quantitative studies that evaluate the use of DA to support pregnant women's decision for peripartum obstetric interventions and to distinguish the effect of these decision aids between low- and high-risk pregnancy. We want to answer three specific questions: What are the main findings of reviews about the effectiveness of DA for peripartum obstetric interventions? What are the characteristics of the existing primary studies about the DA for peripartum obstetric interventions? What are the outcomes measured of the DA for peripartum obstetric interventions according to these studies?

Method: We will include studies involving pregnant women, irrespective of obstetric risk, socioeconomic, or literacy status, that evaluate DAs for peripartum obstetric interventions (e.g. caesarean section). Only studies that used DAs meeting the International Patient Decision Aid Standards (IPDAS) criteria will be included. We will exclude studies on prenatal screening and contraception. The search strategy will cover several electronic databases (including MEDLINE, Cochrane DSR, and EMBASE) and be complemented by reference list screening. We will assess DA quality using IPDAS and summarize findings from existing reviews and primary studies according to DA type, setting, and participant characteristics. Findings will be reported in according to the PRISMA-ScR guidelines.

Keyword: pregnant women, peripartum obstetric intervention, decision aid, childbirth choices.

BACKGROUND

Decision aids (DA) are tools designed to empower patients and enhance communication with healthcare providers(1) by making their decisions explicit, providing information about options associated benefits/harms, and helping clarify congruence between decisions and personal values(2). Patients who are more active in making decisions about their health have better health outcomes and healthcare experiences(3)(4). A DA has three complementary objectives: (i) explicitly states the decision of the patient between different care options that needs to be considered; (ii) provide evidence-based information about the benefits and harms of different options; (iii) help patients to recognize the values-sensitive nature of the decision and to clarify, either implicitly or explicitly, the value they place on the benefits and harms(1)(2).

Pregnancy is a critical period in a woman's life, marked by numerous changes and decisions related to the prenatal, labor and delivery care. Women's engagement in healthcare decision-making during childbirth has been increasingly emphasized as a priority in maternity care, since it increases satisfaction with the childbirth experience and provides health benefits for women and newborns(5)(6)(7). Making decisions about obstetric interventions during peripartum care (e.g. Induction of labor, analgesia, episiotomy, caesarean section) may be challenging for pregnant women, as it requires handling the unique task of weighing the benefits and harms of treatment for themselves against the benefits and harms for their unborn child. Although several obstetric interventions are effective in managing complications of labor and delivery, they are not necessary for the majority of women, particularly low-risk women with a single full-term pregnancy in cephalic presentation who are eligible for a trial of labor. The overuse of unnecessary interventions, such as caesarean sections, can be potentially harmful and represent a misuse of resources(8)(9).

Consequently, DA are now frequently used during pregnancy to support shared decision-making and can be delivered in diverse media formats, including booklet, audio-CD, audio taped booklet, computer-based decision aids apps and online bots(10)(11).

Up to 2023, various reviews on the use of DA during pregnancy have highlighted their positive impacts on pregnant women, including increased knowledge, reduced anxiety, and decreased decisional conflict (12)(13)(10). However, most of existing reviews focused on these three specific outcomes and mainly included studies involving high-risk women such as patients with previous caesarean section(12)(13)(10)(14)(15)(11)(16)(17). There is a lack of knowledge about other potential effects of DA, such as the final choice of women on the obstetric intervention or maternal and perinatal outcomes. Moreover, there are few reviews including low-risk women. Consequently, we don't know whether DAs contribute to reduce unnecessary interventions around childbirth.

OBJECTIVES OF THE SCOPING REVIEW

The objective of this scoping review is to map all the quantitative studies that evaluated the effects of DA on women’s decision making about peripartum obstetric interventions and to compare the effects in low- versus high-risk pregnancies. We want to answer three specific questions:

- What are the main findings of existing reviews about the effects of DA on women’s decision making about peripartum obstetric interventions?
- What are the characteristics of the primary studies on DAs for peripartum obstetric interventions?
- What are the outcomes measured in primary studies on DAs for peripartum obstetric interventions?

METHOD

1. Criteria for considering studies for this review

Type of participants

We will include studies involving pregnant women who were able to make decisions about peripartum obstetric intervention irrespective of their obstetric risk (low- or high-risk women – as defined by the author), socioeconomic or literacy status. Studies conducted in all settings (high- middle- or low-income countries) will be eligible for inclusion. We will exclude studies involving non-pregnant women.

Type of concept: the decision aid

We will include studies on decision aid tools, decision support tools, and decision analysis tools in any format, including booklets, brochures, audio-CD, videos, interactive websites, or applications.

We will only include studies that reported the use of DA that fulfilled all three attributes proposed by the International Patient Decision Aid Standards(1):

(i) explicitly state the decision that needs to be considered;
(ii) provide evidence-based information about a health condition, the options, associated benefits, harms, probabilities, and scientific uncertainties;
(iii) help patients to recognize the values-sensitive nature of the decision and to clarify, either implicitly or explicitly, the value they place on the benefits and harms.

We will exclude studies on tools that only helps pregnant women clarify their value without providing information on benefits and harms or tools that only provides information without helping women clarify their values. We will also exclude studies on DA with insufficient details to assess its content. Studies that analyzed bundles or multiple-faceted interventions including a DA (as previously defined) will be eligible for inclusion in the review. Studies that only assessed educational interventions, such as childbirth preparation classes, birth plan, psychoeducation or motivational interventions, will not be included in the review.

Type of context: the peripartum obstetric interventions

We will include studies on the use of DA to help women make an informed choice about any obstetric intervention used during peripartum care such as electronic fetal monitoring, induction of labor, augmentation with oxytocin, instrumental delivery, analgesia, episiotomy, and any type of caesarean section (e.g. pre-labor or intrapartum caesarean section) We will exclude studies that assessed DA for prenatal screening, contraception, or family planning.

Type of studies included.

We will include experimental or quasi-experimental designs including randomized controlled trials (RCT), controlled before-and-after studies (CBA), interrupted time series (ITS), cross-sectional surveys with a propensity score pair, and reviews including studies. We will also include scoping or systematic reviews that include primary experimental or quasi-experimental studies assessing the effects of DA on women's decision making about peripartum obstetric interventions.

We will use the data collection checklist of the Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care Review Group (EPOC) of the Institute of Population Health, University of Ottawa to include RCT, CBA, ITS studies (18):

Randomized controlled trial (RCT) is a trial in which the participants (or other units) were definitely assigned prospectively to one or two (or more) alternative intervention using a process of random allocation (e.g. random number generation, coin flips).

Controlled before and after study (CBA) is a study involving intervention and control groups other than by random process, and including a baseline period for the assessment of main outcomes. We will apply two minimum criteria for the inclusion of CBAs according to EPOC:

- Pre and post intervention data collection periods for study and control sites are contemporaneous.
- Study and control sites are comparable with respect to dominant reimbursement system, level of care, setting of care and academic status.

Interrupted time series (ITS) is a study assessing the change in slope and trend attributable to the intervention. We apply two minimum criteria for the inclusion of ITS according to EPOC:

- Clearly defined point in time when the intervention occurred.
- At least three data points before and three data points after the intervention started.

In the case of duplicate data, where primary studies included in our review are also included in existing reviews, we will include both the primary studies and the reviews. We will transparently report any instances where overlap occurs and provide a clear distinction between the information obtained from the reviews and the primary studies. We will exclude qualitative studies, and observational studies.

2. Search Strategy and information sources:

The search strategy was developed with the assistance of an expert librarian specialized in health services research. It included three main concepts: target population (pregnant women), decision aid, and peripartum obstetric intervention.

We will search the following electronic databases for articles published from database inception up to December 3, 2023 via the login of Université Paris Cité: MEDLINE, Cochrane DSR, ACP Journal Club, CCTR (Center for Clinical and Translational Research), HTA data base, NHSEED, CINAHL, EMBASE, and PsycInfo. The complete search strategy for each database can be found in Appendix 1. There will be no language restrictions.

The electronic search will be complemented by screening the reference lists of relevant systematic reviews and of articles selected for full text reading.

3. Process of study selection

All references identified in data bases will be imported into Covidence (Melbourne, Australia) and duplicates will be excluded.

Three reviewers (T.P.N., A.P.B and A.D.), working in pairs, will independently screen the titles and abstracts of identified citation. We will retrieve the full text of all citations deemed potentially relevant for full text assessment. Two independent reviewers will read each study and include those that fulfilled the selection criteria. We will document reasons for exclusion of full-text studies. Disagreements between reviewers in the screening, eligibility and inclusion phases will be resolved through discussion or consultation with the third reviewer, if necessary.

The process of study selection will be presented according to the PRISMA-ScR flow diagram and reporting recommendations.

4. Data extraction process

Data from eligible studies will be extracted using a form created for this review that will be piloted by two independent reviewers and modified, if needed, to obtain a final version. The form will capture key study characteristics (study design and period, population, intervention and comparator, key outcomes) and information on all metrics used to describe the effects of DA on women's decision making (see extraction form in Appendix 2). The primary reviewer (T.P.N.) will be responsible for charting data from each eligible article; a second reviewer (A.B.P., A.D., M.R.T., and N.C.) will check each extraction for accuracy. Any discrepancies or disagreements will be resolved through discussion among the reviewers.

5. Assessment of the quality of the decision aid.

The quality of the decision aid tool will be assessed according to the International Patient Decision Aid Standards (IPDAS)(19). There are different criteria to assess the development process, the content of DA, and whether the effectiveness of DA was evaluated. Number of criteria varied according to the different versions of IPDAS.

6. Analysis

Summary of main findings from existing reviews: For each eligible review, we will count the number of primary studies included that potentially meet our inclusion criteria. We will summarize the main findings of existing scoping or systematic reviews. This summary will report DA outcomes and effectiveness, types of settings and populations involved.

Characteristics of primary studies: We will categorize primary studies by type of country where the research was conducted (high, middle or low-income country), setting in which DA

was used (health care facility, clinics, home), DA format (booklet, Apps, web-based, other), DA complexity (evaluated as a simple or complex intervention), characteristics of participants (high or low-risk pregnant women – as defined by authors), type of peripartum obstetric intervention, and study design.

Outcomes measured in primary studies: We will summarize the different outcomes measured in primary studies to assess the effects of DA on participants' decision making about peripartum obstetric intervention. We will conduct sub-group analysis according to the type of participants (low-risk *versus* high-risk women) and setting.

7. Reporting

The findings will be reported according to the PRISMA extension for scoping review (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist (Appendix 3) (20).

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APPENDIX

1. MeSH term strategy on PubMed
2. Extraction From
3. PRISMA for systematic review protocols (PRISMA-P) checklist.

Appendix 1: MeSH term strategy on PubMed

("Decision Support Techniques" [Mesh] OR "Decision Support Techniques" OR "Decision Support Techni*" [TIAB] OR "Technique, Decision Support" [TW] OR "Technic, Decision Support" [TW] OR "Model*, Decision Support" [TIAB] OR "Decision Support Model" [TIAB] OR "Decision Modeling" [TIAB] OR "Decision Modeling" OR "Modeling, Decision" OR "Decision Aid*" [TIAB] OR "Aid, Decision" [TIAB] OR "Decision Analys*" [TIAB] OR "Analys*, Decision" [TW] OR "Decision Making, Shared" [Mesh] OR "Decision Making, Shared" OR "Shared Decision making" [TW] OR "Decision Support Systems, Clinical" [Mesh] OR "Decision Support Systems, Clinical" OR "Clinical Decision Support System*" [TW] OR "Clinical Decision Support*" [TW] OR "Decision Support*, Clinical" [TW] OR "Support*, Clinical Decision" [TW] OR "Birth plan" [TIAB])

AND ("Parturition"[MeSH] OR "Childbirth" [TW] OR "Delivery, Obstetric" [Mesh] OR "Deliveries, Obstetric" [TW] OR "Obstetric deliver*" [TW] OR "Pregnancy"[Mesh] OR "Pregnan*" [TW] OR "birth" [TW] OR "fetal monitoring" [Mesh] OR "fetal monitor*" [TIAB] OR "Monitoring*, Fetal" OR "cardiotocography" [Mesh] OR "CTG" [TIAB] OR "peridur*" [TIAB] OR "intrapartum pain relief"[TIAB] OR "episiotomy" [Mesh] OR "Labor, Induced" [Mesh] OR "Induction of Labor" [TIAB] OR "labor induc*" [TIAB] OR "induced labor" [TIAB] OR "induced, labor" [TIAB] OR "induction, labor" [TIAB] OR "Cesarean Section" [Mesh] OR "C-section*" [TIAB] OR "Cesarean Section*" [TIAB] OR "Delivery, Abdominal" [TIAB] OR "Abdominal Deliver*" [TIAB])

Emtree strategy on Embase:

("Decision Support Techniques" OR "Decision Support Techni*" OR "Technique, Decision Support" OR "Technic, Decision Support" OR "Model*, Decision Support" OR "Decision Support Model" OR "Decision Modeling" OR "Modeling, Decision" OR "Decision Aid*" OR "Aid, Decision" OR "Decision Analys*" OR "Analys*, Decision" OR "Decision Making, Shared" OR "Shared Decision making" OR "Decision Support Systems, Clinical" OR "Clinical Decision Support System*" OR "Clinical Decision Support*" OR "Decision Support*, Clinical" OR "Support*, Clinical Decision" OR "Birth plan")

AND ("Parturition" OR "Childbirth" OR "Delivery, Obstetric" OR "Deliveries, Obstetric" OR "Obstetric deliver*" OR "Pregnancy" OR "Pregnan*" OR "birth" OR "Delivery, Obstetric" OR "fetal monitoring" OR "fetal monitor*" OR "Monitoring*, Fetal" OR "cardiotocography" OR "CTG" OR "peridur*" OR "intrapartum pain relief" OR "episiotomy" OR "Labor, Induced" OR "Induction of Labor" OR "labor induc*" OR "induced labor" OR "induced, labor" OR "induction, labor" OR "Cesarean Section" OR "C-section*" OR "Cesarean Section*" OR "Delivery, Abdominal" OR "Abdominal Deliver*")

('Decision Support Techniques'/exp OR 'Decision Support Techniques' OR 'Decision Support Techni*':ti,ab OR 'Technique, Decision Support':tw OR 'Technic, Decision Support':tw OR 'Model*, Decision Support':ti,ab OR 'Decision Support Model':ti,ab OR 'Decision Modeling':ti,ab OR 'Decision Modeling' OR 'Modeling, Decision' OR 'Decision Aid*':ti,ab OR 'Aid, Decision':ti,ab OR 'Decision Analys*':ti,ab OR 'Analys*, Decision':tw OR 'Decision

Making, Shared'/exp OR 'Decision Making, Shared' OR 'Shared Decision making':tw OR 'Birth plan':ti,ab)

AND ('Parturition'/exp OR 'Childbirth':ti,ab OR 'Delivery, Obstetric'/exp OR 'Deliveries, Obstetric':tw OR 'Obstetric deliver*':tw OR 'Pregnancy'/exp OR 'Pregnan*':tw OR 'birth':tw OR 'Delivery, Obstetric'/exp OR 'fetal monitoring'/exp OR 'fetal monitor*':ti,ab OR 'Monitoring*, Fetal':ti,ab OR 'cardiotocography'/exp OR 'CTG':tw OR 'peridur*':ti,ab OR 'intrapartum pain relief':ti,ab OR 'episiotomy'/exp OR 'Labor, Induced'/exp OR 'Induction of Labor':ti,ab OR 'labor induc*':ti,ab OR 'induced labor':ti,ab OR 'induced, labor':ti,ab OR 'induction, labor':ti,ab OR 'Cesarean Section'/exp OR 'C-section*':ti,ab OR 'Cesarean Section*':ti,ab OR 'Delivery, Abdominal':ti,ab OR 'Abdominal Deliver*':ti,ab)

Appendix 2: Extraction form

Study identification
Author: Journal: Published date:
Study context
Country: Setting Study period: Participants: Type of population (high-risk/low-risk): Sample size: Type of obstetric intervention:
Methodology used
Study design: Format of decision aid:
Results
<i>Tick off for the presence of the outcome reported.</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Final choice <input type="checkbox"/> Actual choice implemented <input type="checkbox"/> Knowledge score* *Knowledge tests based on information contained in the decision aid. The proportion of accurate responses is transformed to a percentage scale ranging from 0% (no correct responses) to 100% (fully correct responses). Decision conflict scale: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• <input type="checkbox"/> Informed subscore• <input type="checkbox"/> Values clarity subscore• <input type="checkbox"/> Support subscore• <input type="checkbox"/> Uncertainty subscore• <input type="checkbox"/> Effective decision subscore <input type="checkbox"/> Anxiety <input type="checkbox"/> Maternal satisfaction <input type="checkbox"/> Maternal outcomes <input type="checkbox"/> Perinatal outcomes Other outcomes
Quality of the decision aid (IPDAS criteria)
IPDAS Score: Version of IPDAS used:

Appendix 3: PRISMA for systematic review protocols (PRISMA-P) checklist

Section and topic	Item No	Checklist item	Page#
Title			
Identification	1a	Identify the report as a protocol of a scoping review	1
Update	1b	If the protocol is for an update of a previous scoping review, identify it as such	Not applicable
Registration	2	If registered, provide the name of the registry (such as JBI) and the registration number	Not yet published
Authors			
Contact	3a	Provide name, institutional affiliation, email address of all protocol authors; provide physical mailing address of corresponding author	1
Contributions	3b	Describe the contributions of the protocol authors and identify the guarantor of the review	1
Amendments	4	If the protocol represents an amendment of a previously completed or published protocol, identify as such and list changes; otherwise, state plan for documenting important protocol amendments	Not applicable
Supports			
Sources	5a	Indicate sources of financial or other support for the review	1
Sponsor	5b	Provide the name of the review funder and/or sponsor	1
Role of sponsor of funder	5c	Describe the roles of funder(s), and/or sponsor, and/or institution(s), if any, in developing the protocol	1
Introduction			
Rationale	6	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is ready known. (Note: Consider providing a rationale for the choice of conducting a scoping review as compared to other evidence synthesis approaches)	2-3
Objectives	7	Provide an explicit statement of the question(s) the review will address with reference to the inclusion/ exclusion criteria	4
Methods			
Eligibility criteria	8	Specify the study characteristics (such as PICO, study design, setting, timeframe) and report characteristics (such as years considered, language, publication status) to be used as criteria for eligibility for the review	5-6

Information sources	9	Describe all intended information sources (such as electronic databases, contact with study authors, trial registers or other gray literature sources) with planned dates of coverage	6
Search strategy	10	Present draft of search strategy to be used for at least one electronic database, including planned limits, such that it could be repeated	6
Study records			
Data management	11a	Describe the mechanism(s) that will be used to manage records and data throughout the review	7
Selection process	11b	State the process that will be used for selecting studies (such as two independent reviewers) through each phase of the review (that is, screening, eligibility, and inclusion)	7
Data collection process	11c	Describe planned method of extracting data from reports (such as piloting forms, done independently, in duplicate), any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators	7
Data items	12	List and define all variables for which data will be sought (such as PICO items, funding sources), any preplanned data assumptions and simplifications (Note: Scoping reviews may not use PICO and instead may use JBI's Population, Concept, and Context [PCC] or another approach to reporting eligibility criteria)	7-8
Outcomes and prioritization	13	List and define all outcomes for which data will be sought, including prioritization of main and additional outcomes, with rationale (Note: Scoping reviews may not extract outcome data, so this can refer to whichever data items are extracted)	7-8
Risk of bias in individual studies	14	If this is to occur, describe anticipated methods for assessing risk of bias of individual studies, including whether this will be done at the outcome or study level, or both; state how this information will be used in data synthesis (Note: Scoping reviews typically do not include risk of bias assessment, but this information should be described if it will occur)	Not applicable
Data synthesis	15a	Describe criteria under which study data will be presented (Note: Scoping reviews do not typically include quantitative synthesis of study data, but should still describe in advance how extracted data	Not applicable

		are anticipated to be presented in the resulting review)	
	15b	Describe the planned approach to how extracted data will be presented (such as figures, tables, evidence gaps maps)	7-8
	15c	Describe any proposed additional analyses (such as thematic analyses) (Note: The JBI methodological guidance does not recommend undertaking thematic analysis, as this synthesis of data should ideally occur following methodological appraisal of the included sources)	Not applicable
	15d	If quantitative synthesis is not appropriate, describe the type of summary planned	Not applicable
Meta-bias(es)	16	Specify any planned assessment of meta-bias(es) (such as publication bias across studies, selective reporting within studies) (Note: Scoping reviews typically do not include assessment of meta-bias(es), but this information should be described if it will occur)	Not applicable
Confidence in cumulative evidence	17	Describe how the strength of the body of evidence will be assessed (such as GRADE)	Not applicable

GRADE, Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation; PICO, participants, intervention, comparator, outcomes; PRISMA, Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses.